

www.maajournal.com

Mediterranean Archaeology and Archaeometry, Vol. 19, No 1, (2019), pp. 121-131
Open Access. Online & Print.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2586001

EASTERN NECROPOLIS OF CYME: TRANSITION FROM CREMATION TO INHUMATION AND GRAVE TYPES

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Received: 01/03/2019

Accepted: 30/03/2019

ABSTRACT

The ancient city of Cyme, located in the Aliğa district of Izmir, was a member of the Aiolis Union and was founded by immigrants from Greece at the end of the second millennium BC. In three separate periods, excavations were carried out in the necropolis in the east of the city and a total of 343 graves were uncovered. These graves dating from the eighth century BC to the first century AD show the process of transition from the practice of cremation to inhumation and provide information about burial customs and grave types. Nine different grave types were used for burials.

KEYWORDS: Cyme, necropolis, cremation, inhumation, grave type, burial customs

1. INTRODUCTION

Cyme, one of the 12 cities of the Aiolis Union, is located on a plain between two hills (Fig. 1A,B). The city is on the seacoast, 6km south of Aliaga in Izmir Province. Although there are no definite records revealing when the city was established, it is generally accepted that it was founded by migrants from Thesaly in Greece at the end of the second millennium BC.

The Venetian Aristide Baltazzi carried out the first excavations in Kyme in 1874–1877, followed by S. Reinach and E. Pottier, who directed excavations in the necropolis in 1881. Excavations at Cyme continued intermittently thereafter until 2015.

Many industrial establishments based on iron and steel and port management are found around Cyme in the third degree archaeological site. Therefore, Izmir Archaeology Museum carried out rescue excavations on the industrial lands. Since ancient necropoleis were generally built outside of a city, the necropoleis were brought to light by these rescue excavations. Three necropoleis were excavated in

Cyme: the southern necropolis (Cırak, Kaya 2011: 217), the Samurlu 877 necropolis (Urkmez 2014: 337) and the eastern necropolis.

The eastern necropolis of Cyme begins about one kilometre from the hill south of the city (Fig. 1B) and is located on terrain which slopes slightly from west to east. In the excavations here, a total of 343 graves were found: in 2007–2008, 35 graves (La Marca 2010: 404–47), in 2010–2012, 145 graves (Korkmaz, Gürman 2012: 69–93) and in 2012, 164 graves (Atıcı, Karakas 2013: 229–242).

The eastern necropolis was used from the second half of the eighth century BC until the first century AD. Many grave types have been unearthed dating back to this broad time period. The graves in the cemetery dated to the early period are cremations, and the graves dated to the late period are inhumations. With these graves, the dates of transition from cremation (the burning of the dead body) to inhumation (burial in the ground by hollowing out a trench in the earth for the body or covering it with rocks or dirt) can be approximately determined.

Figure 1, Map of Cyme and East necropolis

2. EARLY GRAVES

Those dated to the early period were cremation graves and nine of these were found. Four of these graves were well preserved, while the others were obliterated by later graves. However, the four well-preserved graves provide sufficient information about when the cemetery began to be used and the end date of the cremation practice.

2.1. Cremation graves

In the ancient Greek world, first cremations are seen from transition the Sub-Mycenaean to the Proto-geometric Period (Desborough, 1952: 1–2). In the early period, as a general rule, male graves displayed neck-handled amphorae, whereas in women's graves, belly-handled amphorae were used (Desborough, 1952: 5). Children, however, were ex-

cluded from this practice (Desborough, 1952: 1). According to the belief, the purpose of cremation was to destroy the flesh surrounding the body, thus releasing the soul and allowing the person to be at peace.

In a cremation burial, two different practices were observed. In the first method, the cremation was carried out in the cemetery area, and then the bones were collected and, together with the burial gifts, were placed in a container (urn) and the burial process was completed. Examples of this type of practice are Grave 143 (late seventh century BC) and Grave 145 (last quarter of the seventh century BC) in the eastern necropolis of Cyme. In the second method, after the body was laid on the grave area, fuel was laid on top of it and the burning process carried out. As the burning continued, offerings were thrown into the fire. After the fire was extinguished, the bones and offerings there were collected with care and, without being placed in an urn, were covered with a thin layer of soil (Hurmuzlu 2003: 243). Thus, the grave was about 20–30cm in height and appeared as a slight bump. Discarded offering vessels were found in the form of scattered fragments.

As the transition from cremation to inhumation changed from region to region, it is also known that the two customs were practiced together for a long time (Kurtz, Boardman 1971: 72–74). As we shall see in detail below, inhumation burials began to be seen in western Anatolia from the end of the seventh century BC, and this transition process continued until the fourth century BC.

The earliest dated grave in the eastern necropolis of Cyme is the stemmed krater having the inventory number HBS KRT 53 (Fig. 2A). This type of stemmed krater began to be seen for the first time in the Middle Geometric I period (Coldstream, 1968: 17). Standard forms had reached the Middle Geometric II period and from this time began to be used in the graves (Coldstream, 1968: 17, 23). Stemmed kraters, popular in the Late Geometric Period, along with large amphorae were used as grave markers (Kurtz, Boardman 1971: 51, fig. 4; Coldstream 1968: 33).

Stemmed kraters are found in many centres during the Late Geometric Period but are especially abundant in Attica (Brann 1962: pl. 5, no. 92) and Euboea (Boardman, 1952: 6). The spout added to the krater was a popular practice in Euboea and Attica (Coldstream, 1968: 191; Boardman 1952: 6). The thin cream slip on the krater, the chevron motif on the lip, the dotted-lozenge row in the handle region, and the vertical zigzag motifs are characteristic features of Euboea Island and the vessel was probably imported from Euboea (no apotropaic symbols are found on decoration of vases, see Lazarou, 2019). Similar examples found in Athens (Brann, 1962: 42,

no. 92) and Euboea (Boardman, 1952: 6; Coldstream 1968, 191–192) indicate that this krater is dated to the third quarter of the eighth century BC.

Grave 143 (Fig. 2B), a chytra urn used as a container. The globular-bodied, single-handled samples found at the agora of Athens are dated to the late seventh century BC (Brann 1962: 55, no. 210). The examples in Clazomenae are dated to the second half of the seventh century BC using context finds (Hurmuzlu 2003: 376, fig. 10, 31, 33). It is difficult to date chytrae as they were produced in the same form for many years. However, a local production aryballos was found in Grave 143. Such globular aryballos were produced during the Early Corinthian Period, late seventh century BC, (Weinberg 1943: 64, no. 238–39) and it is in accord with the date of the chytra. In Grave 143, the cremation was conducted in the cemetery, right next to the grave. The collected bones and ashes were then placed into the urn. The cremation site can be seen next to the urn (Fig. 2B).

Grave 145 (Fig. 2C), a grey shoulder-handle amphora used as an urn. The cremation was also carried out right next to this grave. Since the ground water level is high, the site of the cremation procedure has been obliterated. However, dense carbon and ash remain in the mud. After the cremation, the remaining bones and ashes were placed into the amphora and the burial process was completed. Decorated samples of these amphorae specific to Aiolis have been dated in an appropriate manner. However, it is difficult to date grey specimens such as that of Grave 145. However, when we look at the development of the form, it can be seen that the early specimens are short and wide necks with high shoulders, globular bodies, and outwardly opening handles. The projection point is in the middle of the body. With time, the form tends to become longer and slimmer, the neck is lengthened and the handles become more steeply angled. Grave 145 has a globular body, long neck and outwardly opening handles. Iren evaluated decorated amphorae similar to this type as being within the Punktstil II group dated to the last quarter of the seventh century and the beginning of the sixth century BC (Iren 2003: 16–24, taf. 2–3, no. 14–20).

HBS KRT 132, the amphora (Fig. 2D) with this inventory number is decorated in Orientalising style. A meander design is seen on the neck, plant and geometric motifs on the shoulder and a wavy line motif on the body. The neck, shoulder, body, underbody and base are separated from each other by glazed bands. This amphora has a thinner, longer body than that of Grave 145, with upright handles, and shows late features. Amphorae with this type of decoration system were classified by Iren as TSIIIa and dated from the end of the seventh century to the

first quarter of the sixth century BC (Iren 2003: 76–84, taf. 29, no. 89). The HBS KRT 132 Amphora is the latest cremation grave found in the eastern necropo-

lis of Cyme. Hence, the first quarter of the sixth century BC can be considered as the period of transition from cremation to inhumation in Cyme.

Figure 2. Cremation graves, A: Earliest cremation grave, stemmed krater, B: Urn cythra, late seventh century BC, C: Urn Amphora, late seventh century BC, D: Urn amphora, late seventh century BC

2.2 Early Inhumation Graves

The process of burying the body without burning is called 'inhumation'. The cause of the transition from cremation to inhumation is uncertain. The transition period varied from region to region, from city to city. The earliest inhumation in the eastern necropolis of Cyme is Grave 78 (Fig. 3A), dated to the late seventh century BC. The corpse of a child, without being burned, was placed into the pyxis, which was placed vertically in the pit. The mouth was covered with a stone and the burial process was completed. This type of globular pyxis was being produced in Athens from the Protogeometric Period (Kraiker & Kubler 1939: taf. 50, no. 599). In early examples, the transition from the shoulder to the body is via a sharp angle, while the handles are joined at a right angle to the body. A pyxis dated to the Early Geometric Period in Corinth, although its decoration is different, is similar to that of Grave 78 in form (Weinberg 1939: 13, pl. 7, no. 37). Many pyxides of this type were found in the Skoubris cemetery in Lefkandi and are dated from the Middle to the Late Geometric Period (Popham & Sachtell 1980: 121, Tomb 33, no: 33.8, pl. 102; 129–30, pl. 109, Tomb 59). A small pyxis in Clazomenae dates back to 620–600 BC (Hurmuzlu, 2003, 355, fig. 14, no. 71/3). In Siracusa, a Corinthian pyxis with a high rim and flattened body dates back to 550 BC (Payne 1931: 323, fig. 164, no. 1326). The flower rosette motif seen on the shoulder area of the vase is a filling motif frequently seen in northern Ionia in the Early Orientalizing Period. Similarly, the vertical spiral motif used to differentiate flower rosettes shows characteristics of this period (Aytaclar 2005: 23–24, fig.10, M.1; 30–31). Grave 78 is decorated in Early Orientalising style and, when both the decoration and the form are considered, should be dated to the third quarter of the seventh century BC. Since children were given inhumation burial from the beginning of the Geomet-

ric Period, Grave 78 does not indicate the commencement date of the inhumation practice in Cyme. However, Grave 133 (Fig. 3B) is important for our understanding of the transition from cremation to inhumation. With the help of a lydion and a miniature vessel coming from Grave 133, we can date this grave. In the first comprehensive study on lydion Greenewalt defined his first group and classified it as "*Type I, Fat Bellied Lydions: The lip flanged with flat or slightly bowed mouth, the neck fairly high and outspreading, body is globular, the foot is short and conical. Many of these are in addition banded on mouth and shoulder*" (Greenewalt 1966: 6). This definition is that of the M133 lydion in Cyme. This type of lydion was found in the grave of Alyates and is dated to 560 BC (Greenewalt, 1966: 69–70, pl.1d). Similar lydion found in Gordion and Manisa date back to 575–550 BC (Cahill 2010: 491, no. 110 from Gordion; 515, no. 145 from Manisa).

The two Clazomenae sarcophagi (Grave 21 and Grave 33, Fig. 3C) found in the necropolis provide important information for the transition from cremation to inhumation. Evaluating Clazomenae sarcophagi in the light of new finds, Hurmuzlu divided these types of sarcophagi into four groups according to form (Hurmuzlu, 2003: 407). The similar sarcophagi of Grave 21 and Grave 33 were classified by Hurmuzlu as "Fourth Group: Simple geometric decorated sarcophagi" and using context findings were dated to the years 580–550 BC (Hurmuzlu, 2003: 419–420, fig. 85).

The Grave 145 and Inventory No. HBS KRT 132 amphorae indicate that there was a cremation custom in Cyme between the end of the seventh century and 575 BC. Grave 133 (dated to 575–550 BC) and Grave 21 and Grave 33 (dated to 580–550 BC) are inhumations. Thus, the transition from cremation to inhumation in Cyme took place during the years of the second quarter of the sixth century BC.

Figure 3. A: Cremation pyxis, B: Earliest inhumation grave, C: Clazomenian terracotta sarcophagus, D: Lekhytoi from fourth century, E: Stone cist grave, F: Lekhytos from fourth century, G: Tile-roofed grave, H: Unguentarium

3. GRAVE TYPES

In the eastern necropolis, which has been used since the Late Geometric Period, cremation burials are seen in the early graves. Different grave types

occur with the transition to inhumation. There are nine different types of graves found in the eastern necropolis: a) Simple ground burials, b) Stone cist graves, c) Tile-roofed graves, d) Stone sarcophagi, e)

Terracotta sarcophagi (Clazomenian sarcophagi), f) Rock-cut chamber tombs, g) Pithos graves, h) Amphora graves and, i) Tumulus graves.

3.1. Simple ground burials

This involves digging the grave in the ground and burial of the dead without any further procedures. There are 146 simple burials in the eastern necropolis, with over 80 of these having stone covers. These graves have no significant orientation. There are graves in the east-west, north-south and north-east-south-west directions, depending on the area of the cemetery. Although the position of the dead is generally dorsal, in Grave 41, the body is lying on its side facing north and the legs are slightly retracted. All the bodies laid on their backs have their arms at the sides or over the abdomen in a unified format.

When we consider grave offerings, there are none in the vast majority of the graves. On the other hand, some of the graves contain simple offerings, while rich offerings have been left in some others. This shows that there was no relationship between the simple ground burials and the economic status of the deceased. The earliest simple burial, as mentioned above, is Grave 133, which is the earliest dated inhumation burial. This grave is dated to the second quarter of the sixth century BC. Grave 43 and Grave 52 were found to have two miniature lekythoi, which are completely identical to each other (Fig. 3D). This type of lekythos, belonging to the Bulas group, is dated to the first half of the fourth century BC in Olynthus (Robenson, 1900: 183, no. 494, taf. 147) and *Dascylium* (Tuna-Nörling, 1999: 54, no. 300–301). The red-figure technique found in Grave 58 is dated to the third quarter of the fourth century BC in the form of a palmet-decorated lekythos (Sparks, Talcott, 1970: 154, no. 1123–28). A palmet-decorated lekythos was found in Kerameikos in a layer dated 338–317 BC (Kovacsovics, 1990: 134, taf. 60, no. 73–75).

3.2 Stone cist graves

In this type of grave, after digging the pit where the body was to be buried, the inner walls of the pit were covered with stone blocks and the burial was then carried out. In the eastern necropolis, 17 stone cist graves were found. There is no common orientation in the stone cist graves. The graves are north-east-south-west or east-west oriented. All skeletons are in the dorsal position. Offerings were found in all graves. In Grave 8 (Fig. 3E), particularly rich offerings were found, which included a gold diadem, 35 gold beads, an iron object preserved in three parts and a coin. Although we do not have enough information about when the cist graves began to be used, a lekythos belonging to the Bulas Group found in

Grave 95 (Fig. 3F) indicates that such graves existed in the mid-fourth century BC.

3.3 Tile-roofed graves

In the necropolis, 95 graves of this type were found. In this type of grave, after the body was buried in a pit dug in the ground, the grave was covered with tiles in the form of a roof. The placement of the tiles was completed in three different styles. In the most extensive application, six tiles were placed together in three rows so as to form a roof (Fig. 3G). In another example, three roof tiles were placed on the grave to form a one-sided slope sealing the grave. In the last type, after the body was buried, the tiles were laid flat on the ground. Unlike other types, graves of this type have a common orientation. All the graves are oriented in an east-west direction. The dead are in dorsal position. Some of the graves had been destroyed, but offerings were observed in all the surviving graves. The unguentaria found in the tiled graves are all of the same form and dated to the first half of the third century BC (Fig. 3H) (Rotroff 2003: 69, no. 253, pl. 43).

3.4 Stone sarcophagi

The necropolis yielded 35 limestone sarcophagi, all of which were made in a similar fashion. Although the lengths of the sarcophagi varied according to the height of the individual, their width measured 75–85cm, depth 60–70cm and wall thickness 8–10cm. (Fig. 4A). There are some differences in the sarcophagus lids. In two graves (Grave 32, Grave 118), there are no covers. Roof tiling was used as a cover in one grave (Grave 116). In other graves, a rectangular stone block or a triangular roof profile block was used. The graves have no common orientation. Although most of them are in the east-west direction, the sarcophagi have been placed to meet the circumstances of the cemetery. Offerings were not left in all of the graves, whereas rich offerings were left in Grave 6, Grave 7 and Grave 20. The earliest example of this type of sarcophagus is Grave 7. In Athens, similar examples of the black-glazed miniature lekythos (Fig. 4B) found in this grave are dated to 410–400 BC (Sparkes, Talcott 1970: 154, no. 1137, pl. 38). In addition, the D Type pyxis found in Grave 7 (Fig. 4B) is similar to one found in Athens dated to 425–400 BC (Sparkes, Talcott 1970: 177, no. 1309–10, pl. 43). The dates of both containers are in accord with each other. The artefacts found in Grave 20 indicate the date for the latest period of the stone sarcophagi. The unguentaria found in this grave (Fig. 4C) are long-necked, oval-bodied and flat-bottomed. Similar unguentaria found in Kerameikos in Athens were dated from the end of the first century BC to the beginning of the first century AD

(Knigge 1976: 167, no. 406–408, taf. 71; 188, no. E.110, taf. 98). An Aphrodite figurine found in Grave 20 (Fig. 4C) is helpful for dating. A figurine found in Myrina resembling the Cyme Aphrodite was dated to the first century BC (Mollard-Besques, 1963: Pl. 24–25). Aphrodite figurines in a slight S-curve pose,

with a crossed leg and leaning on a column are generally dated from the second to the first century BC (Schock, 2009: 318–19, no. A32–A37, taf. 13–14). This information demonstrates that stone sarcophagi were used from the late fifth century BC until the beginning of the first century AD.

Figure 4. A: Stone sarcophagus, B: Lekhytos and pyxis from fourth century BC, C: Unguentaria and terracotta figurine from first century BC, D: Pithos grave, E-F: Amphora graves, G: Tumulus

3.5 Terracotta sarcophagi

Three terracotta sarcophagi were found in the eastern necropolis: Grave 21, Grave 33 (Fig. 3C) and Grave 112. These sarcophagi, dating back to 580–550 BC, have been mentioned above.

3.6 Rock-cut chamber tombs

In 2008, drilling excavations revealed a chamber tomb carved into the rock in the eastern necropolis. Inside this chamber, where 15 people were buried, the inner wall of the tomb was built with stones bonded together with mortar (La Marca 2010: 405).

3.7 Pithos graves

Two pithos graves (Fig. 4D) were uncovered during the excavations in 2008 (La Marca 2010: 405) and 15 (Atıcı & Karatas 2013: 230–35) during the excavations in 2012, to reveal a total of 17 pithos graves in the eastern necropolis. As with the other graves, there is no unified orientation in the pithos graves. Although the dead were generally placed head down in the pithoi, there are also examples where they are head-up (Atıcı & Karatas 2013: 231). Two skeletons were found in each of three of the pithoi.

3.8 Amphora graves

In the eastern necropolis, 19 amphora graves were found. All of these are Lesbos and Khios amphorae. The earliest dated amphora grave is a grey Lesbian amphora (Grave 17) dated 520–490 BC (Fig. 4E) (Clinkenbeard 1982: 265, no. 4, pl. 70.4). The five Chian amphorae (Grave 12, Grave 16, Grave 31, Grave 87 and an amorphous Chian amphora) in the necropolis exhibit common features. Grave 16 (Fig. 4F) is a long-necked Chian amphora produced in the second half of the fifth century BC (Monakov 1990: Tb. 5, no. 33; Anderson 1954: fig.196; Okan 2003: 54, no.6).

3.9 Tumulus graves

A tumulus grave (Fig. 4G) was uncovered in the excavations carried out in the eastern necropolis in 2014. The tumulus, with a diameter of 40.80m, has a dromos (entrance passage to the grave) on the west side. The burial chamber is in the centre of the tumulus and contains one marble sarcophagus. This tomb was robbed by thieves in ancient times and therefore, unfortunately, no grave offerings could be assessed. Details of this grave have not yet been published; however, based on our preliminary evaluation, it should date from the fifth to the fourth century BC.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the eastern necropolis of Cyme, 343 graves of nine different types were uncovered dating from the

third quarter of the eighth century BC through the early centuries AD. There is no evidence of a grave from tenth and ninth centuries BC in Cyme excavations carried out until now.

The graves dated to the early period are cremations and nine cremation graves were found in the necropolis. The earliest cremation is the stemmed krater in Figure 2A dated to the third quarter of the eighth century BC. The latest cremation is the amphora with inventory number HBS KRT 132 in Figure 2D dated to the first quarter of the sixth century BC. The earliest inhumation in the eastern necropolis is Grave 133 in Figure 3B. A lydion found in this grave is dated to 575–550 BC. These are the dates of transition from cremation to inhumation in Cyme; there was no cremation burial after the second half of the sixth century BC.

Cremation was practiced in Attica during the Geometric Period. Although inhumation burials begin to be observed in the Archaic Period, cremation burials are more numerous than inhumations (Kurtz, Boardman, 1971: 71). In the early part of the Classical Period, the incidence of inhumation and cremation continues in a balanced manner. However, by the fourth century BC, cremation burial had decreased (Kurtz & Boardman, 1971: 96). In Attica, the type of burial was left up to family preference. In the studies conducted, no relationship was found between the grave type and the economic status of the family (Kurtz & Boardman, 1971: 96–97). Although there were still cremation graves in the Hellenistic Period, inhumations made up a large proportion of the burials (Kurtz & Boardman 1971: 162–63).

In western Anatolia, the situation was similar to that of Attica. There was no specific collective date when cremation shifted to inhumation as the transition took place as a process. The custom of inhumation in Clazomenae emerged at the end of the seventh century BC; however, cremation had ended by the beginning of the sixth century BC (Hurmuzlu 2003: 241–45). Cremation burials in Ialysos and Kamiros continued until the last quarter of the sixth century BC (Gates 1983: 19). In Miletus, as in Attica, up to the Hellenistic Period the practice of cremation was seen to decline (Folbeck, 2016: 21–30). In Assos, the custom of inhumation began in the middle of the sixth century BC, while cremation continued up to the Hellenistic Period (Stupperich, 1992: 15). Consequently, the transition from cremation to inhumation in western Anatolia started from the middle of the seventh century BC, with cremation burials continuing to decrease until the Hellenistic Period (Hurmuzlu 2003: 240–45; Gates 1983: 18–20; Kurtz, Boardman 1971: 68–69). In the eastern necropolis of Cyme, no further cremation was conducted after the

introduction of inhumation in the second quarter of the sixth century BC.

The reason for the transition from cremation to inhumation is a controversial issue and precise research data on this topic are not yet available to us. However, during the first thousand years BC, cremation burial was not practised in Lydia (Baughan 2010: 273–304). Especially after the reign of King Alyattes (590–560 BC), the Lydians began to dominate the Ionian cities of western Anatolia and cultural interaction was intensified (Kerschner, 2010: 247–66). In the time of Alyattes and Croesus, Ephesus, Smyrna and Cyme came under the rule of Lydia. The end of the custom of cremation in Cyme and the initiation of the custom of inhumation can be explained by the influence of Lydia. Moreover, the presence of a lydion produced in Lydia in the earliest dated inhumation grave supports this idea.

When we look at the graves in the eastern necropolis, no clear unity of orientation can be seen. However, the graves lie mostly in the east-west and north-east-south-west directions. Although the position of the skeletons is generally dorsal, the bodies were laid on their sides in several graves.

When we look at the offerings in the graves, a connection between the grave type and the economic status of the deceased is noteworthy. In the simple ground burials, the offerings are very few and have no value, while the stone cist and sarcophagus graves exhibit an increased number of offerings consisting of more valuable items. Similarly, the construction of the cist graves must be related to economic status as some of the cist graves are made with simple stone blocks, while in a number of others, the blocks display high-quality workmanship.

The most common type of grave is the simple ground burial. The rock tomb, which held 15 different skeletons, and the tumulus emerged as unique grave types. The rock tomb most likely had belonged

to a family. In terms of its size, splendour, grave chamber and the workmanship of the sarcophagus, the tumulus must have belonged to a ruler of the region.

When we compare the eastern and southern necropolis of Cyme (Cırak & Kaya 2010: 217–32), although there is no difference between the types of graves, richer offerings were found in the southern necropolis, including a great deal of gold left as offerings. According to the available data, these two cemeteries, which were used at almost the same periods, indicate a class separation between rich and poor.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it was understood that in the eastern necropolis of Cyme, used from the eighth century BC until the first century AD, the early period graves were cremations, and the late period graves were inhumations. Different types of vessels were used in the cremation burials, while nine different types of inhumation graves were determined. The graves have no common orientation and they were probably designated according to the empty spaces in the cemetery. No relationship was found between the grave types and the financial status of the individuals. The Euboean stemmed krater, the Clazomenae sarcophagi and the Lydian lydion in the cemetery are evidence of cultural and commercial relations with these regions. The most important finding was the determination of the date of transition from cremation to inhumation in the eastern necropolis of Cyme. Although differences were observed among regions, the transition from cremation to inhumation in Cyme occurred in the second quarter of the sixth century BC. This transition was most likely related to Ionia and southern Aiolis coming under Lydian domination during this period.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to thank Mehmet Tuna who Director of Izmir Archaeology Museum and Archaeologist Erdal Korkmaz and Archaeologist Beyhan Gurman who are carried out Eastern necropolis excavation.

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